

D6.4 DEMONSTRATION OF CIRCULAR USE IN FLEXIBLE FOOD PACKAGING BASED ON CFP TECHNOLOGIES

WORK PACKAGE 6

Associated Task(s):

Task 6.4: LOOP 3: PE PCRs from TBS waste,
circular use in flexible food packaging

Task 6.5: Implementation by packing
and lifetime tests, evaluation and
guidelines for industrial take-up

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PUBLISHABLE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main objective of Work Package (WP) 6 is to demonstrate and validate the circularity of flexible food and non-food packaging. This work package explores how recycled material from three different waste sources can be reused in novel packaging applications, showcasing the quality of post-consumer recyclates (PCRs) obtained through the recycling processes established in WP3.

LOOP Scenarios

The project focuses on three primary loop scenarios for recycling flexible packaging:

LOOP 1 investigates the recycling of flexible packaging from households, demonstrating how dissolution recycling with pre- and post-treatment technologies can improve recyclate quality for reuse in home and personal care packaging.

LOOP 2 explores a closed-loop business-to-business (B2B) collection system for flexible food packaging. This system ensures that recycled material can be used again in food packaging.

LOOP 3 consists of two cycles designed to simulate the repeated use of recycled material in packaging and assess the impact of a second recycling step on material properties. This loop incorporates tracer-based sorting (TBS) to separate food from household flexible packaging waste and by this way creates a close-loop system for flexible food packaging. Various recycling cascades are explored to achieve the highest quality recyclates. The goal is to reuse the resulting PCRs in food packaging.

The insights gained from these loops provide valuable recommendations for designing circular food packaging and optimizing recycling cascades. Six different demonstrators were produced to validate these results, covering three application areas: food packaging, home care packaging, and personal care packaging. Different laminate structures were designed to incorporate PCRs into flexible food and non-food packaging, and technologies required for achieving circularity in flexible packaging were outlined.

This Deliverable **D6.4** presents the circular use of polyethylene (PE) post-consumer recyclates (PCRs) produced from Tracer-Based-Sorted (TBS) food packaging waste in LOOP 3. The process started with state-of-the-art mono-material PE flexible food packaging marked with fluorescent tracers, which were mixed with real flexible household waste. Following TBS, the sorted food packaging items were shredded, washed, deinked, mechanically recycled, and deodorized. The resulting PE PCRs were then re-incorporated into recyclable, mono-material PE flexible food packaging again. This procedure has been repeated in 2 Cycles, so-called LOOP 3 Cycle 1 and LOOP 3 Cycle 2.

Two types of flexible food packaging demonstrators were produced:

- **LOOP 3 Cycle 1:** A flexible packaging containing 50% PE PCR content, used for coffee packaging. The shelf life of the product was predicted using water vapor transmission rates and moisture content analysis for coffee and cocoa powder products.
- **LOOP 3 Cycle 2:** Flexible packaging produced with 34% PE PCRs from Cycle 1 input waste, tested for cocoa powder packaging.

D6.4 provides a detailed overview of the food packaging specifications, TBS demonstration, recycling processes, laminate production with PE PCRs, and performance test results. It builds on previous results from WP2, WP3, WP5, and deliverables D2.6, D3.6, and D5.4. Additionally, the deliverable mentions the environmental impact of the recycling scenario and cost considerations, with further insights available in Deliverables D7.5 and D8.4.

Within **LOOP 3**, comprising **two cycles**, the CIRCULAR FoodPack project carried out a demonstration of a long and extensive process chain at large scale. Initiated as early as Month 13 of the project, it allowed the project to make significant progress, whereby it had to rely on the best partner technologies available at the given time. Consequently, it could not always incorporate the most optimized sorting and recycling technologies developed later in the project at scale and thereby paves the way for further advancements and improvements.

Sorting and Recycling Results: The sorting of food packaging from flexible household packaging waste was successfully achieved using the TBS technology. The sorting process achieves a high purity rate of over 98%, with advanced Sort4Circle® technology increasing this to more than 99%. This high sorting purity is critical for producing high-quality recyclates suitable for food packaging¹. Although the advanced mechanical recycling process slightly impacted the mechanical properties of the recyclates, it was still possible to extrude second-cycle PCRs and integrate them into new flexible packaging materials at a PCR content of 34%.

Packaging Performance: An important finding is the necessity of using functional barriers to safely incorporate PCRs from food packaging into new food packaging. By sandwiching the recyclates between two functional barriers, the migration of unwanted substances into the packaged product can be effectively reduced. These innovative laminates containing PCRs and functional barriers were successfully tested on packaging machinery at Nestlé. However, further research is needed to optimize material properties, confirm the long-term effectiveness of functional barriers in reducing contamination, and simplify testing procedures. Additionally, further exploration into certified recycling methods for producing PE PCRs is required.

In summary, the circular use of PE PCRs coming from TBS flexible food packaging waste has been successfully demonstrated, providing a pathway for their reuse in food packaging applications. These results pave the way for more sustainable packaging solutions, optimizing the recycling process and ensuring product safety.

¹ [COMMISSION REGULATION \(EU\) 2022/1616 of 15 September 2022 on recycled plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with foods, and repealing Regulation \(EC\) No 282/2008](#)

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	
AMCOR-G	Amtcor Flexible in Gent
AMCOR-K	Amtcor Flexible in Kreuzlingen
COF	Coefficient of friction
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
EVOH	Ethylene vinyl alcohol
IVV	Fraunhofer Institute for Process Engineering and Packaging (IVV)
KREYEN	Kreyenborg
LDPE	Low density polyethylene
LSIT	Lowest Seal Initiation Temperature
MDOPE	Machine-direction oriented polyethylene
MFI	Melt flow index
ML	Migration level
OTR	Oxygen transmission rate
PC	Post-consumer
PCR	Post-consumer recyclate
PE	Polyethylene
rPE	Recycled polyethylene
POLY	Polysecure
RH	Relative humidity
SF	Solvent-free
SUP	Stand-up pouch
TBS	Tracer-Based-Sorting
TVOC	Total volatile organic compounds
VOC	Volatile organic compounds
VFFS	Vertical Form Fill Seal Machine
WP	Work package
WVTR	Water vapour transmission rate

1. INTRODUCTION

Task 6.4 aims to demonstrate the successful application of tracer-based sorting (TBS) to separate food from non-food packaging waste. This is a crucial step for enabling the potential use of recyclates in food packaging applications, as outlined by the European Recycling Regulation No. 2022/1616. Furthermore, the task demonstrates the circular use of PE PCRs in flexible food packaging.

Figure 1 below illustrates the process that the traced packaging waste undergoes to be recycled into high-quality recyclate in both LOOP 3 Cycle 1 and Cycle 2.

Figure 1: Recycling cascade for recycled PE (PE PCR) from traced food packaging for high-quality food packaging applications

Two circular uses have been shown within LOOP 3 (Cycle 1 and Cycle 2):

- In Cycle 1, state-of-the-art recyclable laminates from AMCOR with printed tracers, contaminated with coffee from pouch production (NESTLE, Fraunhofer) have been mixed into French household flexible packaging waste, provided by SUEZ. After the sorting of traced food packs with a sorting purity of 97.4% by TBS (POLY), purification and recycling processes have been performed (UGENT, SUEZ, KREYEN). PE PCRs have been produced and characterised including their contamination levels. These are the so-called LOOP 3 Cycle 1 (L3C1) recyclates. The TBS results for L3C1 are discussed within the public Deliverable **D2.6** "Report on TBS

sorting efficiency and sorting trials”, within the 1st Period of the project. The characterisation results of L3C1 PE PCRs are provided in the public Deliverables **D3.6** “Production of PE PCR pellets with a quality of over 0.9 related to processing and mechanical properties compared to virgin pellets”, **D3.7** “Report on developed cost-effective process chains”, and **D4.3** “Characterization of input material, benchmarking of cleaning processes”. The final laminate has been designed for the incorporation of the PE PCRs and produced (AMCOR, POLY, SIEGWERK) with 50% L3C1 PE PCRs. The details of the novel recyclable mono-material based flexible packaging laminate with L3C1 PE PCRs are reported in the confidential deliverable **D5.4** “PE based mono-material laminates with PE PCRs for flexible food and non-food packaging”.

The waste input for L3C1 consisted of 385 kg of tracer-marked food packs, of which 315 kg were TBS-sorted from a total of 632 kg of mixed household flexible packaging waste (including both food and non-food materials).

The output of Cycle 1 was 210 kg of coffee pouches in pillow bag format, produced using a PE mono-material based laminate (i.e., L3C1 laminate) containing 50% L3C1 PE PCR, along with functional barriers and printed tracers.

In Cycle 2, the key difference in comparison to Cycle 1 was that the waste input (coffee pouches) already included 50% PE PCRs. The waste input used in Cycle 2 was the output of Cycle 1, 210 kg of coffee pouches in pillow bag format, produced with the L3C1 laminate containing 50% L3C1 PE PCR, with functional barriers and printed tracers.

As in Cycle 1, the material was sorted, purified, and recycled. PE PCRs from Cycle 2 were produced and characterised. Based on the insights gained from Cycle 1, the incorporation of PE PCR in the final flexible packaging laminates was optimised. Novel laminates were produced with the so-called LOOP 3 Cycle 2 (L3C2) recyclates. These new laminates are referred to as L3C2 laminates.

In this deliverable, Section 2 includes a comprehensive overview of the recycling cascade including the input waste materials used, TBS trials, washing, deinking and mechanical recycling processes applied for the production of PE PCRs, characterisation results of L3C2 PE PCRs in comparison to L3C1, and the newly designed recyclable flexible packaging materials with PE PCR. The performance of these flexible laminates is discussed and summarised in Section 3 for the targeted demonstrator applications.

Figure 2 depicts the complete LOOP 3 flow including Cycle 1 and Cycle 2 with the related material amounts and timing. The red box represents the sorting trials of the second cycle, in which the purity of tracer-based sorting needed to be shown separately, due to insufficient tracers incorporated into the input material of LOOP 3 Cycle 2. This is discussed in Section 2.2.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2: LOOP 3 flow for Cycle 1 and Cycle 2, timelines and quantities, starting with input waste until demonstration (M: project month, C2: Cycle 2, IVV: Fraunhofer, T: Tracer). (a) each step with corresponding partners and time, (b) relevant pictures for each step shown in (a)

2. RECYCLING OF FLEXIBLE POST-CONSUMER PACKAGING

This deliverable presents the results of the LOOP 3 scenario from work package (WP) 6, with more focus on the second recycling cycle (LOOP 3 Cycle 2). Cycle 1 has already been reported in various deliverables as described in Section 1 and also within the 2nd Periodic Technical Report under WP6 (Task 6.4) and will only be briefly summarized here below:

2.1. LOOP 3 Cycle 1 (L3C1) Summary: Tracer-Based-Sorting and recycling cascade

First, 390 kg input laminates with tracer printing were produced by AMCOR and sent to NESTLE for the production of two different packaging pouch types: gusseted pouch and pillow pouch. The pouches produced at NESTLE (385 kg) were then sent to the STEINERT Test & Development Center in Pulheim, Germany, as external partner for the tracer-based sorting trials. Simultaneously, SUEZ supplied 600 kg French mixed flexible post-consumer waste to the sorting site. On site, 315 kg of the tracer-marked pouches and 317 kg of the post-consumer waste² were mixed into 13 big bags, each with an average weight of 38 kg, and left for a week (in summer), to simulate a real contamination. During three days, the waste mix of about 630 kg was sorted in a two-step sorting process into a traced and a non-traced fraction (see Figure 3). A purity of 97.4% could be achieved at an efficiency of 90.2%, which was a great and promising first result.

Figure 3: Material preparation performed within Task 6.3 for LOOP 3 Cycle 1, following the arrow: virgin mono-material food packaging laminates produced by AMCOR; pouches produced

² Due to time and capacity constraints only a subset of the available material could be processed.

at Nestlé; sorted pouches after tracer-based sorting trial from POLY at Steinert; cold-washed and shredded flakes from Herbold as input for the deinking at external partner NTCP

After the tracer-based sorting, the sorted fraction (283 kg) and the remaining unsorted pouches (70kg) were sent to Herbold Meckesheim GmbH (Herbold) for shredding and cold washing. From Month 19 on, these washed flakes were pre-treated in an upscaled deinking and delamination process of UGENT. The deinking process for this shredded material has been upscaled from lab-scale to semi-industrial scale at the external partner National Test Centre Circular Plastics (NTCP). The conditions that worked best in lab-scale at UGENT could not fully be transferred to larger scale at this specific partner, the NaOH concentration had to remain lower. The list below summarises the used parameters:

- Deinking agent concentration 0.5wt%
- NaOH concentration 1.5%
- Ratio plastic/flakes 4.2%
- Defoamer added when required in the process
- Temperature setpoint 80°C
- Hot wash operational time 45 min + 10 min
- Volume solution: 500L

The material was processed in 14 batches, of which Figure 4 depicts samples taken from each batch. It is clearly visible, that the flakes show still blue colouring, which slightly differs from batch to batch.

Figure 4: Overview of samples taken from the 14 deinking batches as input into the recycling process at SUEZ

Figure 5 shows the deinking and the subsequent mechanical recycling steps in more detail. In total, 260 kg were the output of this deinking process, which is a total loss of ~17 %. This loss is significantly higher than expected and estimated in the preparatory discussions. Moreover, this output still contained a humidity of ~15%. After thermal drying at SUEZ, the remaining material accounted to 203 kg.

Figure 5: Material flow scheme in the deinking plant at the external partner NTCP (orange) and subsequent recycling steps at project partner SUEZ (green). Output: 203 kg L3C1 PE PCR to be used in the further LOOP 3 Cycle 2 trials.

The outcome of the recycling cascade as discussed above including deinking, mechanical recycling and deodorisation has been the L3C1 PE PCR granulates that could be converted into new films and laminates (Figure 6). From these 203 kg L3C1 PE PCRs, 13 kg have been sent to AMCOR and Fraunhofer IVV for the basic characterisation of the material and to test the processability of the material before performing large scale trials. It was possible to extrude the films at 100% PCR content. Details on these evaluations are reported in D5.4 of WP5 (Month 30). Based on the results, the large-scale laminate production was conducted at AMCOR as described in Section 2.2.1.

Figure 6: L3C1 Recyclates (left) and extruded films made from it (100% PCR) at Fraunhofer IVV (middle). Flexible laminate (AMCOR) and packaging pouch from this laminate (NESTLE) with coffee filling (right)

2.2. Flexible food packaging waste as input for LOOP 3 Cycle 2 (L3C2) trials

2.2.1. Structure of the L3C2 input material with 50% L3C1 PE PCR

The input waste pouches for LOOP 3 Cycle 2 (L3C2) were produced using a laminate structure produced at an industrial scale by AMCOR, incorporating L3C1 polyethylene post-consumer recyclates (PE PCRs). In total, AMCOR produced 415 kg of flexible laminate material. Of this, 249 kg belonged to Structure 1 laminate (see Table 1, it is referred to as L3C1 laminate), which

contains 50% L3C1 PE PCR and is intended to undergo a second recycling process in L3C2. Additionally, 166 kg of a second laminate (Structure 2) was produced using virgin polyethylene (PE) and a different type of printed tracer. This second laminate was used in sorting trials to demonstrate tracer-based sorting (TBS) into two fractions.

The laminates were converted into coffee packages at NESTLE, and additionally MESPAC (a customer of AMCOR) produced smaller sachets to test the sorting of smaller packages during the L3C2 sorting trials. From the Structure 1 (L3C2 laminate), a total of 179 kg of coffee packages and 31 kg of sachets were produced by NESTLE and MESPAC, respectively. From Structure 2, 135 kg of coffee packages and 19 kg of sachets were made. The difference between material input and output was used for testing and optimization purposes.

The laminate structure 1 (L3C1 laminate) is shown in Table 1 and Figure 7. It contains 50% L3C1 PE PCR and includes tracers to ensure it is identifiable as food packaging during TBS. The PE PCR layer is sandwiched between two functional barrier layers to enable usage in food contact applications. For more details about this new laminate structure see Deliverable D5.4 "PE based mono-material laminates with PE PCRs for flexible food and non-food packaging". More details on the following pouch production at NESTLE for L3C2 trials, and the corresponding shelf-life predictions for two different food products are provided in Section 2.2.3 and Section 2.2.3, respectively.

Table 1: Structure of the mono-material PE based flexible packaging laminate with 50% L3C1 PE PCR for coffee packaging

No.	Layer structure	Related LOOP
Structure 1 (L3C1 laminate)	HPL / MDOPE / P1 / SiO _x / inks with tracer / DDP // L3C1 PE PCR (60 µm) // PE-EVOH-PE (40 µm)	Input for: LOOP 3 Cycle 2

HPL: Heat protective lacquer, DDP: Deinking and delamination primer

The structure includes all the design elements required to make the laminates, and packaging made from it, suitable for the recycling technologies developed within the project. A deinking and delamination primer (DDP) is applied on top of the inks to enable a delamination between the sealing film and the printed inks to remove them in the washing and deinking step. The design also respects the mono-material PE-based concept, to make an advanced mechanical recycling possible and to avoid any other types of materials than PE with a content above 10 %. Moreover, functional barriers are included to sandwich the L3C1 PE PCR film in the core of the structure, based on the barrier screening results of the project. Towards the outside, a combination of an organic (primer, P1) and inorganic coating (silicon oxide, SiO_x) has been selected, towards the inside, a coextruded PE-EVOH³-PE film has been chosen as functional barriers. Thus, all technologies are respected in the design.

³ EVOH: **Ethylene vinyl alcohol** is a copolymer of ethylene and vinyl alcohol.

Production on industrial line (7 step proces)

Figure 7: Left: Structure design using the recyclate resins from Cycle 1 (see Table 1), Middle: gusseted and pillow bag produced from the laminate incorporating 50 % L3C1 PE PCRs, filled with coffee at NESTLE. Right: Three side seal sachet produced at MESPAC from the same laminate.

The sample design was chosen in order to simulate the characteristics of realistic packaging designs with included tracers. The design of the first samples in LOOP 3—the input waste material for L3C1—had been relatively simple to facilitate tracer detection testing, featuring a blue-on-white print pattern consisting of large rectangles, with the fluorescent tracer incorporated in the white print (Figure 3, top left and right). For the L3C2 samples, the design was changed to a complex CMYK print pattern (Figure 7, right), with the tracer incorporated in the yellow print layer instead of the white background layer, thus better resembling a typical commercial packaging design with smaller features and varying print density. Moreover, including the tracer in yellow instead of white demonstrates the usability of tracers in various ink formulations with different properties.

2.2.2. Pillow bags and gusseted bags of L3C1 for coffee beans: Machinability

The main objective of the Vertical Form Fill and Seal (VFFS) packaging machine trial at Nestlé Research Lausanne, was to produce 4 pallets (310 kg) of “artificial” packaging waste with very small amounts of coffee beans inside to simulate remaining product contamination from the consumer after disposal. Beforehand, a technical trial was carried out to evaluate the technical feasibility of running the pillow bag format on this machine type.

The initial assessment focused on empty pillow bag formats (W 140 x H 200–270 mm). Subsequent trials were conducted to fill 400 g of coffee beans at a rate of 40 bags per minute. In Figure 8 (schematic processing of vertical form fill seal machine – VFFS), the image on the left shows the laminate going to the machine for pouch filling and sealing, the middle shows the shoulder for the forming and the sealing, and the right image shows the pillow bag produced.

Figure 8: Schematic VFFS processing of L3C2 input material (in Month 30), from the reel, passing through a forming shoulder, and sealed Vertically and Horizontally, filled, to a Pillow bag

Two conventional sealing jaw profiles designed for plastic laminates were tested for horizontal sealing performance. With Jaw Profile 1 (Tip Seal), 100% tight bags were achieved at 80 bags per minute, with a sealing time of 300 ms under the conditions of 150°C/8000 N and 155°C/6000 N. In contrast, Jaw Profile 2 (Flank Seal) did not achieve fully tight bags at 80 bags per minute and up to 6000 N. The best performance observed with this profile was 95% tight bags at a reduced speed of 70 bags per minute, with a sealing time of 300 ms and conditions of 150°C/6000 N.

When the bags were subsequently filled with coffee beans, performance with Jaw Profile 2 further declined, achieving only 14% tight bags at 40 bags per minute, with 140°C/6000 N, and a sealing time of 400 ms. The high material thickness of 130 μm , combined with a low heat seal layer ($\sim 40 \mu\text{m}$) and a non-optimized machine setup, presented significant challenges in establishing a reliable operating window.

Based on these observations, recommendations included maintaining a total laminate thickness in the range of 90–110 μm and incorporating a higher-performing heat seal layer of 40–60 μm . Machine-side improvements, such as reducing speed, increasing seal time to 400–500 ms, and designing jaws specifically tailored for this material type, were also identified as effective measures to improve tightness and overall machine performance. These insights were applied in the production of the pillow bags. The production process for the coffee pillow bag pouches using this laminate is demonstrated in the accompanying video:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DTkZrohquHw>.

Key learning from the trials performed at NESTLE:

The high material thickness of 130 μm , combined with a thin heat seal layer ($\sim 40 \mu\text{m}$) and a non-optimized machine setup, posed significant challenges in establishing a reliable operating window. Based on these observations, the recommendations include:

- Maintaining a total laminate thickness in the range of 90–110 μm .
- Incorporating a high-performing heat seal layer of 40–60 μm .

In Cycle 2, in the production of the laminate with the L3C2 PE PCR, these recommendations were implemented. The PE PCR content was reduced from 50% to 34%, and the sealing layer thickness was increased to 60 μm for the L3C2 laminate, as discussed in Section 2.5.3.

2.2.3. Validation of shelf-life of packed coffee with L3C1 laminate

Nestlé has developed a shelf-life simulation model to predict the lifetimes of food products based on their sensitivity to moisture and oxygen when packed in various packaging materials. These simulations evaluate the barrier performance of different laminates and estimate shelf-life durations by taking into consideration factors such as pack geometry, temperature and humidity, seal seam geometry, and packaging material thickness. This helps identify suitable packaging materials for different types of food products.

The simulations were conducted using two packaging formats produced on a VFFS Rovema machine at Nestlé Research in Lausanne. Product types evaluated included roast and ground coffee—which typically require a shelf life of 18 to 24 months—and Nesquik cocoa powder.

During packaging production, factors such as the design of forming shoulders and cross-sealing jaws, as well as residual gels, excessive tension, and sealing seams, can compromise barrier integrity. To evaluate these effects, oxygen permeability (OP) and water vapor transmission rate (WVTR) measurements were conducted on 3D pouches after production. Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4 present the OP and WVTR values for the L3C1 laminates, comparing their performance as flat laminates and in 3D pouch form.

Table 2: Oxygen permeability (OP) at 23°C / 50 %RH

Sample	Specimen 1	Specimen 2
L3C1 pillow bag in [$\text{cm}^3 / (\text{Pack} \cdot \text{d} \cdot \text{bar})$]	0.0049	0.006
L3C1 flat sample in [$\text{cm}^3 / (\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{d} \cdot \text{bar})$]	0.0008	0.005

Table 3: Water vapour transmission rate (WVTR)

Sample	Specimen 1	Specimen 2
L3C1 pillow bag @23°C / 85%RH in [$\text{mg} / (\text{Pack} \cdot \text{d})$]	18.1	18.8
L3C1 (flat sample) @38°C/90%RH in [$\text{g} / (\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{d})$]	1.46	1.42

The shelf-life predictions primarily focused on the moisture sensitivity of the products, as moisture uptake is the most critical degradation factor for the selected product categories—roast and ground coffee, and Nesquik cocoa powder. These products are hygroscopic, meaning they readily absorb moisture, leading to quality degradation. For such products, maintaining a water activity (a_w) within the pack below 0.6 is essential to prevent mold growth and ensure product safety. Consequently, only the Water Vapor Transmission Rate (WVTR) of the packaging materials was considered in the analysis, simplifying the approach while ensuring alignment with product requirements.

Table 4: WVTR at 23°C / 85%RH in [mg / (Pack·d)] converted to [g / (m²·d)]

Sample: L3C1 pillow bag	Specimen 1	Specimen 2	AVG	Conditions
mg / (Pack·d)	18.1	18.8	18.45	
g / (m ² ·d)	0.30	0.31	0.31	23°C/85%RH
g / (m ² ·d)	0.75	0.78	0.76	38°C/90%RH

Surface area of the package (m ²)	0.06048
Dimensions	140 mm Width
	250 mm Height
seal	17 mm

Although moisture sensitivity is the primary concern, oxygen permeability also affects product quality, particularly for coffee. Oxidation can cause rancidity, which is a perception-based issue influenced by coffee type and processing. According to literature^{4, 5}), the oxidation threshold is approximately **150 µg/g**, equivalent to **75 mg of oxygen for 500 g of coffee**.

Based on Oxygen Transmission Rate (OTR) measurements, the L3C1 laminate's oxygen barrier performance is exceptionally high (see Table 2). The oxidation threshold of **60 mg O₂ for 400 g of coffee** is not reached even after more than 10 years, based on measurement results that are near the detection limit of the MOCON® Ox-Tran® 2/22 device."

In summary, the shelf-life simulations demonstrated that the L3C1 laminate is well-suited for medium-sensitive products, such as those tested here. For roast and ground coffee, the simulations confirmed that moisture sensitivity is the dominant factor limiting shelf life. As shown in Figure 9, the WVTR of the laminates plays a decisive role, with predicted shelf lives of up to **2.2 years at 20°C and 65% RH** and to **1.3 years at 30°C and 70% RH** for packed coffee and over **2 years** for Nesquik cocoa powder.

While the L3C1 laminate provides excellent performance for medium-sensitive products, further improvements in barrier resilience and sealability are needed to meet the requirements of higher-sensitivity products, such as pure soluble coffee. Future developments in packaging materials will be essential to address these challenges and extend shelf life further. Additionally, conducting shelf-life tests will be essential to validate the predictive models and assess the suitability of novel packaging laminates for selected food product types.

⁴ Radtke R., Chem. Mikrobiol. Technol. Lebensm. 6, 36–42 (1979), Fraunhofer-Institute für Lebensmitteltechnologie und Verpackung and der Technischen Universität München

⁵ Horst-Christian Langowski (2017) 'Shelf life of packed food and packaging functionality' edited by Preeti Singh, Ali Abas Wani, Horst-Christian Langowski, Food Packaging materials, Boca Raton, CRC Press, Chapter 2. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781315374390>,

Figure 9: Shelf-life calculations performed with L3C1 laminate for roast and ground coffee and Nesquik cocoa powder

2.3. Tracer-Based-Sorting (TBS) of flexible food packaging

2.3.1. Summary of TBS trials in L3C2

In L3C1, large scale sorting trials had been performed in July 2022 (Month 15) at the Steinert Test & Development Center⁶ in Pulheim, Germany. The tracer-printed samples were mixed with French flexible packaging background waste in a ratio of 1:1. These trials had resulted in a sorting purity of 97.4% and a yield of 90.2%, as described in detail in **1st Periodic Report** and in **Deliverable D2.6**.⁷ In the trials, the main factor limiting the sorting performance had been determined to be black items in the background stream, namely large black agricultural foils. Larger items have a higher probability of overlapping with other items at usual levels of belt coverage, so they have a tendency to be erroneously ejected together with correctly detected samples. Because black items cannot be detected by NIR spectroscopy, they can also not be separated in a second, negative-sorting step which is used to remove remaining non-traced items from the stream. This type of items is a peculiarity of the French waste used in the trials and is not representative for all European flexible packaging waste streams. Addressing it would require a separate color sorting step.

For the sorting trials in L3C2 – which are reported in detail in **2nd Periodic Report** – the input waste composition was adjusted by using waste from German instead of French collection to

⁶ Steinert Test & Development Center was the subcontractor of SUEZ for TBS trials of Cycle 1 and Cycle 2.

⁷ A video showing the L3C1 sorting trials can be found at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ti200mkjAWI>

avoid the agricultural foils. Also, the mixing ratio of traced pouches to background waste was changed to 1:3, since lower ratios are more representative for the ratio of food to non-food material in some European flexible household waste streams, as evaluated by SUEZ. Technically, lower ratios impose a higher challenge on the sorting purity, because the false positive rate⁸ must be lower to reach the same purity. In the L3C2 trials it was also planned to demonstrate the simultaneous sorting for two different tracer type fractions. To this end, a second set of flexible packaging samples printed with another tracer was prepared (made from virgin PE) by AMCOR, MESPAC (a customer of AMCOR) and NESTLE, and included in the input waste material.

The L3C2 trials were conducted in November 2023 (Month 30). However, due to insufficient tracer signals obtained from the samples, the trials were not successful, and no values on purity and efficiency could be obtained. In a systematic analysis, the issue was traced back to deviations in the tracer concentration, which were influenced by several factors. A detailed analysis of this outcome is provided in the 2nd Periodic Report.

Some observations provide valuable insights into customizing industrial printing processes for tracer printing (see public deliverables **D3.8** “Guidelines on Design for Recycling” and **D5.5** “Guidelines for tracer printing in packaging for effective sorting, management after use”). For instance, as a best practice, a calibration reference for the tracer concentration should be taken directly on the specific machine intended for printing. This is because the tracer transfer function can vary significantly between different printing units, cylinders, and even as a function of ink viscosity. While such calibration can be costly for small batches on industrial lines due to the large amount of scrap material generated, it becomes more feasible if the line is already being calibrated for a new print layout. Additionally, a common practice in printing involves adjusting viscosity or color opacity through on-line dilution. For tracer inks, these adjustments should take into consideration the tracer concentration to ensure consistency. If required, the tracer dosage can also be adapted accordingly.

2.3.2. Repeated sorting trials

To obtain the desired figures, the sorting trials were repeated in May 2024 (Month 36). For the new trials, new samples with adjusted tracer concentration were produced. Printing and lamination of the foils was done by Siegwirk with foils coming from AMCOR-G. Pouch production was done by Fraunhofer IVV at their site in Dresden. Meanwhile, the L3C2 input pouches with PCR content were passed on to the subsequent processing steps (see section 2.4) in order to avoid further delays. Since the key figures of a TBS process with printed tracers are independent of the properties of the underlying bulk material, the results obtained with the new-made samples would also be valid for LOOP 3 material.

The trials took place from 6th to 8th May 2024 (Month 36) at the Steinert Test & Development Center again. The work was carried out by POLY, Fraunhofer IVV and the Steinert team. As before, the input material to the sorting line was made of the marked samples mixed with background flexible packaging waste.

The tracer used in the samples was the same tracer as in the previous Cycle 2 samples. Following the investigation after the previous trials, the concentration was increased from 10 µg/cm²

⁸ False positive rate: Probability that a non-traced item is sorted into the traced-item output fraction

(nominal value) to 40 µg/cm² to obtain sufficient luminescence intensity. As before, the tracer was applied in yellow color, which was printed on top of white background color. The configuration of yellow tracer ink on white background is beneficial for high luminescence intensity at low tracer usage due to low absorption in the yellow layer and high backscattering in the white background layer. The chosen printing layout was a complex design consisting of fields of different print densities, gradients, barcodes and text (see Figure 10), thus mimicking a realistic packaging design.

Figure 10: Samples for the repeated sorting trials with tracer incorporated in the yellow color

In total, 82 kg of pouches were produced⁹. The quantity produced was determined by the available production capacities at Siegwirk (for printing) and Fraunhofer IVV (for pouch production) in Dresden within the available time frame.

The background waste was supplied by Lober GmbH, sourced from German collection. The material ordered was fraction 323-2 of the German Dual System (flexible polyolefin items <300mm), which was requested in loose, uncompressed form, rather than the usual compressed bales. However, due to difficulties faced by the provider in obtaining uncompressed material from a sorting facility, they had to reopen a bale. This was accomplished by processing the bale through a bag opener. Unfortunately, this device, not designed for this specific task, shredded a significant portion of the material into small flakes (<100 mm), which negatively impacted the trials. The total amount of background waste provided was 290 kg, resulting in a ratio of pouches to background waste of 1:3.6.

The samples were mixed into the background waste by feeding batches of both materials in the correct ratio into the input bunker and homogenizing the mixture manually during the infeed

⁹ This quantity constitutes a sufficient sample size to obtain statistically valid results. To calculate the minimum necessary sample size, one can use the formula $n_e = \frac{z^2 \times p(1-p)}{\epsilon^2}$, which gives the sample size n_e in the sorted output fraction (i.e. the number of ejection events). z is the z-score which is derived from the desired confidence level (used value 1.96 for a confidence level of 95%), p is the estimated purity value (used value 95% as a low estimate) and ϵ is the allowed margin of error (0.5%). The formula yields $n_e = 7300$ necessary ejection events. From this, we can calculate back to the needed number of samples in the input stream n by $n = n_e/r$, where r is the ratio of ejection events per input item. To calculate r , we need to know the mean item weight of the samples $m_s = 3g$ (measured) and the background waste $m_w = 3g$ (estimated as equal to sample weight), the ratios of samples $f_s = 29\%$ and background waste $f_w = 71\%$ in the input stream, the true positive rate $p_s = 77.6\%$ and the false positive rate $p_w = 0.4\%$. These numbers can be obtained from the used material quantities and the measured values for purity and yield. Here, they are given for the third sorting run, being the smallest and the most relevant one (see text). The ratio r is given by $r = f_s \times p_s + f_w \times p_w$, and using this one obtains a sample size of $n \approx 32300$ items. In the third sorting run the number of marked samples was about 10.000 and the total number of items 36.000, thus being well sufficient for valid results.

into the sorting line with garden forks. The mixing, combined with the repeated circulation of the material at the transition from the bunker to the elevating conveyor belt, led to a well homogenized input stream.

Figure 11: Left: Batches of samples and background waste. Middle: Manual mixing in the infeed bunker. Right: Sorted output after concentration and cleaning run.

The sorting process consisted of two consecutive steps. In the first step, all marked objects were blown out (positive sorting, “concentration”), leading to a concentrated output with remaining impurities. In the second step, this output was processed again blowing out all non-marked objects (negative sorting, “cleaning”), thus cleaning the stream and achieving very high purity. After the process, each output fraction was hand-sorted and weighed to determine the masses of pouches and waste, from which the numbers for purity of the sorted sample fraction and yield were calculated.

Three complete sorting runs were carried out with the material:

1. In the first run, all material was used as-is. After the first step (concentration), the achieved purity was only 65%, at a yield of 81%. After the cleaning step, the purity reached 84% while the yield dropped to 72% due to additional losses in the cleaning step (Table 5). This very low purity was caused by contamination with a lot of small flakes from the background waste, due to the improper preparation of the waste bale. Because small flakes in such quantities are not to be expected in the considered waste stream (if present, they are normally removed in the sieve drum or in the ballistic separator earlier in the process), the sorter is not designed to process objects much smaller than 100 mm. Therefore, detection and ejection of the small flakes did not work correctly and subsequently these parts were found in both output fractions.
2. To make the background waste more representative of real waste streams, a decision was made to sieve out the small flakes before proceeding with further sorting attempts. This was achieved by processing the material through a ballistic separator, which divided the stream into three categories: large flat objects (primarily the desired flexibles), small objects (including foil flakes), and 3D objects (introduced due to sorting errors at the original facility). The second sorting run focused exclusively on the large flat output material, which was deemed more representative of typical flexible waste streams.

Figure 12: Background waste after processing through the ballistic separator. Left: Large 2D fraction (after usage in the sorting process, thus including some remaining pouch samples), middle: 3D fraction, right: 2D fines (small flakes with 100 mm size).

After the sieving step, the remaining waste quantity was 165 kg. The material was mixed with 66 kg of traced pouches, creating a sample to waste ratio of 1:2.5. This ratio aligns with the proposed target amounts in the DoA. With this input material, the second sorting run resulted in a purity and yield of 80% after the concentration step, and a purity of 93% with a yield of 74% after the cleaning step. It was observed that many erroneous sorting events occurred when clusters of samples were positioned closely together on the belt, or even overlapping. This often led to waste objects being inadvertently swept away with the samples. Minimizing such occurrences requires optimizing the object distribution on the belt and the ejection accuracy.

- Thus, the third sorting run was done with optimized parameters. The belt coverage was reduced, and the timing of the air valves was adjusted. Again, the sample-to-waste ratio was set to 1:2.5. Due to time constraints, the third run could only be conducted with a subset of the available material (77 kg of waste and 31 kg of pouches), but statistically valid results could still be obtained with the reduced quantities. After the concentration step a purity and a yield of 88% and 82%, respectively, were achieved, and after the cleaning step 98% and 78%, respectively (Table 5).

Table 5: Key figures of the sorting trials

	Sorting Run 1		Sorting Run 2		Sorting Run 3	
Input Quantity	82 kg traced pouches + 290 kg background waste		66 kg traced pouches + 165 kg background waste		31 kg traced pouches + 77 kg background waste	
	Concentration	Cleaning	Concentration	Cleaning	Concentration	Cleaning
Purity	65%	84%	80%	93%	88%	98%
Yield	81%	72%	80%	74%	82%	78%

The final purity of 98% is only slightly below the target of 99%. It is believed that 99% could have been achieved with further optimization of the process parameters. However, due to the time lost during the first run and the cleaning of the background waste, it was not possible to conduct additional runs.

Despite the challenges, it has been demonstrated that very high purities of the sorted fraction can be achieved with the TBSlight system, at acceptable yields. The improvement in results over the course of the runs indicates that the sorting outcome is highly dependent on the composition of the waste stream and the adaptation of mechanical system parameters to suit this particular stream. This is expected to be the limiting factor in any industrial application, while the tracer detection itself is sufficiently reliable to enable very high purities. Therefore, objects must be well separated on the belt, and overlapping must be minimized to reduce the likelihood of ejected objects unintentionally carrying others with them. This requirement applies to all sorting lines using pneumatic ejection and is not specific to tracer-based sorting.

2.3.3. Sort4Circle® sorting trial

Following the observation of insufficient tracer concentrations in the L3C2 samples, an additional sorting trial was conducted at the Sort4Circle® (S4C) test line for small parts at the POLY technical lab (see Figure 13). The Sort4Circle® technology allows the usage of detectors with much higher sensitivity than equipped in an NIR sorter and is therefore able to detect signals at much lower tracer concentrations. S4C introduces a novel sorting scheme, in which the items are first singulated, then transported through a detection stage where each item is measured individually, and subsequently the item is transferred to the endpoint corresponding to the determined measurement result. Unlike an NIR sorter, the separation step after the detection is not done with pneumatic air nozzles but (in the present case) by folding down the trays of a tray sorter. Therefore, mechanical ejection errors are completely eliminated.

Figure 13: Sort4Circle® test sorting line at POLY. Parts are carried from the input bunker through a singulation stage into the tray sorter and through two detection stages (currently tracer and color measurement). Subsequently, deposition into up to 7 outputs.

The sorting in the trial was done in one pass, without a cleaning step. The items were fed by hand into the sorter, since the currently implemented singulation stage of the test line is designed for small rigid parts (shredded waste) and cannot handle flexibles well. In “manual” operation mode, the small sachets made by MESPAC (those sachets prepared for L3C2 TBS Sorting at scale, as discussed in Section 2.3.1) could be sorted with the sorter. As background waste, flexible household waste items were cut to processable size and also fed in by hand. The trial was conducted with 111 samples of L3C2 material (with Tracer 1), 99 of the samples with the Tracer 2 and approx. 316 items of background waste. In order to increase the statistical significance, two consecutive test runs were carried out with the material.

The objects could be sorted to very high purities of 99.4% for the Tracer 1 samples and 99.2% for the Tracer 2 samples. Moreover, very high sorting efficiencies of 96.8% and 100.0%, respectively, could also be achieved, which means that almost zero (Tracer 1) or even exactly zero (Tracer 2) traced items were discarded with the background waste (Figure 14). This outcome shows that it is possible to sort extremely reliably even at very low tracer concentrations of 10 µg/cm² and less, if the technology is specifically suited and adapted to conventional packaging sorting lines and if the mechanical restrictions like air nozzles are eliminated.

Figure 14: Sorted samples after Sort4Circle® process. Left: Pouches with Tracer 2. Middle: Pouches with Tracer 1. Right: Background waste

2.4. Washing, deinking and mechanical recycling

2.4.1. Washing and deinking

Deinking upscaling was performed on LOOP 3 Cycle 2 (L3C2) material at Hydrodyn¹⁰. Prior to upscaling, the deinking and delamination conditions for L3C2 material were first optimized at lab scale at UGent. To improve delamination and deinking efficiency, various parameters were investigated, including solid/liquid (S/L) ratio, contact time, second wash with fresh medium, temperature, and surfactant type. For example, it was observed that this material requires longer contact time (>2 hours) to achieve complete delamination compared to LOOP 3 Cycle 1 (L3C1) material. Additionally, significant color staining remained on the material after the deinking process, with changes to process parameters yielding no substantial improvement in staining. To address this, a water-based deinking process using scavengers was developed at UGent. Based on lab-scale process optimization tests conducted at UGent, the decision was made to incorporate a scavenger in the upscaling trials at Hydrodyn for deinking the green L3C2 material. Initially, 20 kg of material was shredded into 2 cm flakes, and the deinking process was conducted at 75°C for 2 hours. The process conditions included a 1% solid consistency, 5% NaOH concentration, 0.5% detergent concentration, and 0.08 % scavenger concentration.

¹⁰Hydrodyn is the subcontractor of UGENT (for deinking at scale) for LOOP 3 Cycle 2 material.

However, residence time was not sufficient to effectively delaminate the material. In the second trial, 20 kg of material was processed under the same operational conditions, but the interaction time with the liquid medium was extended to 4 hours. As the results were promising, these conditions were used for deinking 120 kg of material at Hydrodyn in September 2024. The deinked material was shipped to Suez for densification and granulation, followed by deodorization at KREYEN.

Compared to the L3C1 material, the deinking and delamination conditions, as well as the subcontractor, differed for the LOOP 3 Cycle 2 (L3C2) material. Structural differences between these two materials required adjustments to the optimized process conditions. L3C1 material consists of 2 layers of LDPE with either white or blue ink between the layers of polymer (MDOPE/SiOx/DDP/ink/Solvent free Adh/Seal PE), whereas L3C2 material has triplex structure as given in Table 1 and Figure 7. Upscaling deinking test of L3C1 was performed by using NTCP (Netherlands) semi-industrial scale hot wash process. The process was carried out by using a formulation provided by Siegwirk (PolycirQ P2) in 14 different batches of 21.5 kg (see Figure 4). Most of the batches were washed in two steps of 45 and 10 min. Compared to L3C2 material, shorter interaction time was sufficient for deinking and delamination of L3C1 material. Regarding the process conditions, the deinking trial of L3C1 material was performed at 80°C, with a 1.5 % concentration of NaOH and a 4.2 % ratio of flakes/water. The use of higher NaOH concentrations was not feasible at the subcontractor, which negatively impacted deinking efficiency. As with the L3C2 material, color staining was also observed on the L3C1 material following the deinking process. Since the use of scavengers to prevent color staining had not been developed at that time, an additional washing step was introduced after deinking. The plastic flakes were re-fed to the line for 10 min (after 45 min deinking) at the same processing conditions. It was observed that this rinsing step holds paramount importance in the deinking process, serving as a crucial stage for eliminating residual ink, NaOH, and deinking agent from the material. After the deinking process of L3C1 material, 203 kg of PE PCR has been produced at SUEZ for the laminate production at AMCOR as already discussed in Figure 5.

2.4.2. Mechanical recycling and deodorization of traced flexible packaging waste containing L3C1 PE PCR

For the LOOP 3 Cycle 2, 120 kg of flakes (Figure 15, second picture) provided by UGent after the deinking trial realised at Hydrodyn were processed in a first step of densification on an Intarema 504K equipment from EREMA. The process conditions were the following:

- Densification at 90°C
- Extruder at 170°C
- Die at 160°C.

118,5 kg of densified pellets (Figure 15, third picture) were produced. After densification, the pellets were homogenized in a co-rotative twin-screw extruder LTE26-44 from Labtech (Diameter 26, 44D) with degassing. To increase the OIT, 5 % of antioxidant was added. The process conditions were the following:

- Extruder at 220°C,
- Filtration at 112 µm.

After the last step of the process, ~113 kg of recycled PE pellets (Figure 15, fourth picture) were produced by extrusion and sent to KREYEN for thermal treatment.

Figure 15: First: Input waste for L3C2; Second: Sample of flakes after deinking at Hydrodyn; Third: Sample of pellets after densification; forth: sample of rPE after extrusion

The 113 kg sample received from Suez was deodorised at KREYEN: First, the material was subjected to an infrared treatment in the IR-Batch 120/100 drum, followed by a thermal treatment in a 0,75m³ conditioner for the final odour treatment (Figure 16).

Treatment parameters: IRD 20min @ 90°C, Conditioner 8h @ 90°C, air flow 250 m³/h. After deodorization, ~100 kg material was passed on to AMCOR-G for laminate production.

Figure 16: Deodorization process at the project partner KREYEN. Left: deodorisation in drum. Right: after deodorisation

2.5. L3C2 PE PCR film and laminate production for food packaging

2.5.1. Volatile organic compounds analysis of L3C2 PE PCR before extrusion

Prior to the extrusion trials, the L3C2 PE PCRs received from SUEZ by AMCOR were evaluated for their total volatile organic compound (TVOC) levels to ensure safe processing on-site. Current safety requirements mandate the use of powered air respirators when processing any PCR or

compostable resin with a TVOC (boiling point < 100°C) content exceeding 10 mg/kg, or a TVOC (boiling point < 200°C) content exceeding 20 mg/kg. These thresholds set practical limits for the processability of post-consumer recyclates.

The initial samples prior to deodorization (Samples 1 and 2, see Table 6) exhibited high VOC levels. Their TVOC content was close to the 10 mg/kg limit for compounds with a boiling point below 100°C and exceeded the 20 mg/kg limit for those with a boiling point below 200°C. Specifically, the initial sample had a TVOC (BP < 200°C) exceeding 27 mg/kg.

In contrast, the deodorized sample demonstrated a significantly lower TVOC (BP < 200°C) of 4.6 mg/kg. At this reduced level, the deodorized resin no longer required the use of air respirators during processing on a blown film line. This result confirms that the deodorization process applied by KREYEN effectively reduced VOC content to a level where VOC-related safety concerns are eliminated.

Table 6: TVOC content of recyclates before and after deodorization

Grade	Name	TVOC (BP<100) [mg/kg]	TVOC (BP<200) [mg/kg]
L3C2	Sample #1	8.2	27.7
L3C2	Sample #2	9.8	32.5
L3C2	De-odorized	2.6	4.6

2.5.2. Film extrusion trials with 100% L3C2 PE PCR

The L3C2 PE PCR pellets were extruded in a 40 µm film with 100% PCR content. The material showed a lot of gels and a lot of fumes (Figure 17), nonetheless extrusion was possible. The details of the extrusion parameters are shown in Table 7 below. The final width was 550 mm in order to proceed with the lamination step afterward.

Table 7: Report from AMCOR pilot extrusion on blown film parameters

General					
Haul Off Speed	19 m/min	Total Thickness	40 µm	Haul Off Temp	70 °C
Blown Width	650 mm	Min. Thickness	35 µm	Prim NIP Tension	80 N
Film Width	550 mm	Max. Thickness	46 µm	ewind TensionR	50 N
Treatment	g-layer	Range	11 µm	Frame	IN
Frost Line Height	0 cm	Actual Thickness	41 µm		
BlowUp Ratio	2.7587	Qn	2.758886		
Roll Length	0 m	Spreading	14.8 %		
Core Diameter	96 mm	Cooling Temp.	20 °C		
Roll Diameter	96 mm	Ventilator Speed	20 Hz		

Figure 17: Extruded films with 100% L3C2 PE PCR

2.5.3. Laminate production with L3C2 PE PCR

The L3C2 PE PCR is intended for use in flexible food packaging. To achieve this, the laminate structure shown in Figure 18 was used. It consists of a triplex laminate, with the PE PCR layer sandwiched between two functional barriers. Demonstrator packaging items were designed in various formats, including a gusseted or pillow bag for coffee beans and a stand-up pouch for cocoa powder. The requirements for these food applications were defined at the start of the project (see Deliverable D5.1) and are summarized in Table 8. The laminate containing the L3C2 PE PCR was specifically used for packaging cocoa powder.

A laminate structure with 34% L3C2 PE PCR content was produced on the pilot lines at AMCOR and subsequently tested in packaging trials on packaging machines. Figure 19 shows some meters of the produced laminate, the roll on the right is the L3C2 laminate with 34% L3C2 PE PCR. It shows the effect of the developed scavengers in the optimised water-based medium, resulting in the deinking efficiency (>95% Cu removal in L3C2, 90% Cu removal in L3C1) improvements, leading to a more transparent material in comparison to the LOOP 2 laminate (see Deliverable D6.3 "Demonstration of circular use in flexible food packaging based on B2B collection"), although the deinking upscaling tests for LOOP 2 and L3C2 materials were conducted at the same subcontractor (Hydrodyn).

The reduction of the PE PCR layer thickness from approximately 60 μm to around 40 μm , combined with the increase in the sealing layer thickness from about 40 μm to 60 μm , helped address the challenges encountered in Cycle 1. Pillow pack formats for cocoa powder was produced using a vertical form-fill-seal packaging line, as detailed in Section 3.2. Additionally, a stand-up pouch format was produced with printing by the AMCOR Catalyst™ team. However, the structure exhibited gels and bubbles, visible on both printed and unprinted demonstrators after production. The performance of the laminates in the selected demonstrator formats is discussed in Section 3.

Figure 18: Laminate structure (referred as L3C2 laminates) used for the production of the demonstrator packaging material at AMCOR for cocoa powder (MDOPE (23 μ m) / L3C2 PE PCR (~44 μ m) / Sealing layer (60 μ m))

Table 8: Requirements for Flexible Packaging Materials Used in Food Packaging Demonstrators

Criteria	Gusseted/Pillow Bag - coffee	SUP – Cocoa powder
COF in/metal and in/in (dyn)	Smooth curve below 0,35 dynamic / 0,4 static	Smooth curve below 0,35 dynamic / 0,4 static
Bi-oriented film in structure	At least 20 μ m	At least 20 μ m
Bond strength [N/15mm]	2-5 N	2-5 N
Seal strength [N/15mm]	1,5 – 2 N	1,5 – 2 N
Stiffness (MD, GPa)	$\geq 20 \mu\text{m} \times 1,5 \text{ GPa}$	$\geq 20 \mu\text{m} \times 1,5 \text{ GPa}$
WVTR (38°C, 90%RH)	$< 1,4 \text{ g/d/sq.m}$	$< 5 \text{ g/d/sq.m}$
OTR (23°C, 50%RH)	$< 0,5 \text{ cc/d/sq.m}$	$< 600 \text{ cc/d/sq.m}$
PCR content	30% wt laminate VOC safety limit according to AMCOR ML safety limit according to Fraunhofer $< 20 \text{ gels/dm}^3$ with $D > 200\mu\text{m}$ MFI goal of 0,8-4 g/10min	30% wt laminate VOC safety limit according to Fraunhofer ML safety limit according to Fraunhofer $< 20 \text{ gels/dm}^3$ with $D > 200\mu\text{m}$ MFI goal of 0,8-4 g/10min
Overall thickness	Typically 80 μ m – below 120 μ m	Typically 80 μ m

Figure 19: Laminate produced at AMCOR with L3C2 PE PCR: Left without and right with the scavengers in the wash media (UGENT development) during the deinking at Hydrodyn

3. PERFORMANCE OF LAMINATES WITH PE PCRS AND THE DEMONSTRATORS

3.1. Mechanical performance

3.1.1. Mono-layer film of L3C2 PE PCR compared to L3C1 PE PCR

Table 9 shows performance values of the monolayer film containing 100% PE PCR (L3C2) produced at AMCOR in comparison to the results obtained with the L3C1 monolayer film including the density, melting temperature, oxidation initiation time (OIT) and melt flow rate (MFR) of the PE PCR pellets. All values are within the expected range for further converting processes. There is no significant deviation observed in the density and melting behaviour of the L3C2 in comparison to L3C1 PE PCRs. The comparison of the differential scanning calorimetry measurements is shown in Figure 20.

A comparison of properties such as OIT, MFR, and mechanical characteristics reveals differences in recycle quality between the two cycles. The higher OIT observed in Cycle 2 may be attributed to the stabilizers used during the production of LOOP 3 Cycle 1 PE PCR s. The input laminate material for LOOP 3 Cycle 2 consisted of 50% PE PCR from Cycle 1, and stabilizers were added again at the same concentration during the production of Cycle 2 PE PCR. Analytical detection would be helpful to determine the cause of the OIT increase.

Table 9: Properties of Mono-layer blown film of L3C2 in comparison to L3C1

PROPERTY	UNIT	VALUE L3C1	VALUE L3C2	TEST METHOD
GENERAL				
Name	-	PE PCR L3C1 (100%)	PE PCR L3C2 (100%)	-
Type	-	PE granulate	PE Granulate	-
APPEARANCE				
Color	-	Blue green	Light green	-
Shape	-	pellets	pellets	-
PHYSICAL				
Density		0.921 ± 0.001	0.909 ± 0.003	ISO 1183-1
Melt Flow Index (MFI)	[g/10 min]	0.812	1.051	ISO 1183-1
OIT	Min	> 14	> 38	ISO 11357-6
Melting Temperature (first peak / second peak)	[°C]	107 / 124	108 / 125	ISO 11357-3
Mechanical properties – blown film (MD: Machine direction) (*)				
E Modulus	MPa	258	202	ISO 527
Tensile strength	MPa	27	18.0	ISO 527
Strain at break	%	530	444	ISO 527
Tensile break strength	MPa	26.3	17.5	ISO 527
Yield strength	MPa	8.9	9.5	ISO 527
(*) L3C1 and L3C2 were characterised at 500 mm/min (at AMCOR)				

The L3C1 and L3C2 tensile tests were performed by a Hounsfield 1 ST tensile tester using a load cell of 250 N at 500mm/min at AMCOR. The slight decrease in mechanical properties observed in Cycle 2 can be, on the one hand, attributed to polymer and contaminant degradation during multiple processing cycles or, more likely, to the higher proportion of inclusions (such as gels and bubbles) present in the films made from L3C2 PE PCR.

Figure 20: Differential Scanning Calorimetry results measured for L3C1 (top) and L3C2 (bottom) PE PCRs

3.1.2. Bond strength of the laminates

Figure 21 presents the bond strength test conditions in a table, along with the measured bond strength values of the triplex laminate produced with L3C2 PE PCR film, MDOPE-P1-SiO_x (shown in Figure as [MDOPE SiO_x]) and PE/EVOH/PE sealant. The PCR film side exhibits a very high bond strength to the PE sealant, well above the desired 2.5 N/15mm. In contrast, the lamination of the PCR film against the SiO_x system proves to be slightly more challenging, though it still achieves the minimum required bond strength. The results are considered satisfactory, as they exceed the 2 N/15mm threshold, which is the minimum acceptable for recyclable-ready structures.

Analysis n°							
A20-xxxx	Bond Strength						
Settings:	Tensile tester						
Apparatus:	Hounsfield 1 ST						
Apparatus n°:	989/016						
Load cell:	250 N						
Pull velocity:	100 mm/min						
Pull direction:	Cross Direction						
Pulling angle:	90°						
Sample width:	15 mm						

Figure 21: Bond strength of the L3C2 laminate (left column between PCR and PE-EVOH-PE, right column between SiO_x and PCR).

3.1.3. Sealing range

The seal curve is determined by measuring the seal strength when sealing the material from 80°C to 170°C (or until the material starts to show degradation). In the graph below shown in Figure 22, stable seal strength is reached at 120°C and the material starts to seal at 100°C. These are standard values for Mono PE laminates. These results have been used in the packaging trials to set-up the sealing temperatures in the machine.

Analysis n°	Seal Curve				ASTM F88
A20-xxxx					
Settings:	sealing equipment				Tensile tester
Apparatus:	Brugger HSG-C				Apparatus: Hounsfield 1 ST
Apparatus n°:	989/414				Apparatus n°: 989/016
Pressure:	300 N/15cm ²				Load cell: 250 N
# heated seal bars:	2				Pull velocity: 300 mm/min
Seal time:	0,5 s				Pull direction: across the seal
Seal direction:					Sample width: 15 mm
Sealed against:	Itself (inside/inside)				
Protected by:					

Figure 22: Sealing curve of the L3C2 laminate

3.1.4. Coefficient of friction

Coefficient of friction (COF) is measured to foresee any issues of the unwinding of the film inside the packaging machine against the metal element. On the COF from the inside to the metal, results are in range with expectations (0.2-0.3) while the COF from the outside to the metal is a bit on the higher side (Table 10). However, this has not caused any problems during the demo pouch production.

Table 10: Coefficient of friction values measured for the outside and inside of the L3C2 laminates

Analysis n°											
A20-xxxx	Coefficient of Friction										ASTM D-1894
Settings:											
Apparatus: Monitor slip & friction - model n° 32-06 (TMI)											
Apparatus n°: 989/208											
Sled: B											
Velocity: 150 mm/min											

inside - metal

	m1	m2	m3	average	SD
Static	0.272	0.339	0.292	0.301	0.034
Dynamic	0.226	0.263	0.234	0.241	0.019

outside - metal

	m1	m2	m3	average	SD
Static	0.633	0.637	0.616	0.629	0.011
Dynamic	0.515	0.503	0.523	0.514	0.010

3.2. Processing performance and summary

3.2.1. Processing performance - Machineability

The laminate produced with the L3C2 PE PCRs served two purposes: the majority (approximately 60 kg) was used at AMCOR for packaging trials on the vertical form-fill-seal packaging line, while a smaller portion was used to create a demonstrator pack, showcasing the end product as it would appear on store shelves. In the latter case, a food demonstrator for cocoa powder was produced in a stand-up-pouch (SUP) format by the AMCOR Catalyst™ team. A visual representation of the SUP demonstrator's technical design is shown in Figure 23. It includes the LOOP information, project number, and application details, while additional information is provided via a QR code and a link to the project website.

The processing performance of the material was assessed on a vertical form fill seal machine. The format produced is a pillow pouch format that is also used to pack cocoa powder in the Beverage market Figure 24. The analytical data presented in section 3.1.1 to 3.1.4 was used in the setting up of this packaging machine (Figure 25). Despite the higher COF outside/metal, the material ran in the machine without issues.

The pouches were evaluated in terms of hermeticity via a Inficon device (vacuum decay method). Vacuum decay testing relies on the principle of a gas flow from a sample package into a vacuum chamber. Gas coming out of the sample into the vacuum chamber causes a pressure rise in the

vacuum chamber, which can be measured by a transducer. This rise in pressure can be measured over a certain time period and related to the leak size. The faster the pressure rise, the larger the observed gas leak.

Figure 23: Design used by Catalyst™ team for the Cocoa powder demonstrator

Figure 24: Pillow pack format (contains resin pellets) Using the material on the machine, its operating window was determined testing different speeds and sealing temperatures

Figure 25: Pillow pack for Cocoa powder production at AMCOR on vertical form fill seal packaging line.

The operating window is shown in Table 11; for a given speed (expressed in ppm: packs per minute) and temperature of the horizontal and vertical seal, the hermeticity of 10 bags is measured. When the result is above 0.01 mbar.l/s the bag is considered not tight which means the integrity of the product inside can be compromised.

To conclude the study of processing performance of the L3C2 material, the operating window table shows that it is possible to make hermetic pouches even at the highest operating speed. However, the operating window is quite narrow in comparison to virgin PE laminates. Indeed, most of the combinations of speed and temperature give either a non-hermetic pouch (shown in red color in Table 11) or alternatively caused issues in the packaging machine when forming the pack (i.e. “sticks to the jaws”).

Table 11: Operating window for L3C2 laminate on the vertical form fill seal packaging line at AMCOR

Run N°	Speed	T° horizontal seal	T° vertical seal	Average Inficon result	Comment
40	40	120	150	0.404	
41	50	120	150	0.4398	
42	40	120	160	0.112	
43	50	120	160	0.28	
44	40	120	170	0.0642	
45	50	120	170	0.1954	
46	40	120	180	0.0488	
47	50	120	180	0.1014	
25	40	130	150	0.0014	
26	40	130	160	0.014	
27	40	130	170	0.004	
28	40	130	180	0.1392	
29	50	130	150	1.864	
30	50	130	160	1.864	
31	50	130	170	0.018167	
32	50	130	180	0.014857	
1	40	140	150	0.001167	Sometimes they stick to the jaws
2	40	140	160	0.001	Sometimes they stick to the jaws
3	40	140	170	0.001	Sometimes they stick to the jaws
4	40	140	180	0.001	Sometimes they stick to the jaws
13	50	140	150	0.0815	
14	50	140	160	0.0118	
15	50	140	170	0.001	
16	50	140	180	0.001	
5	40	150	150	0.1415	Wrinkled seal
6	40	150	160	#DIV/0!	Stick to jaws
7	40	150	170	#DIV/0!	Stick to jaws
8	40	150	180	#DIV/0!	Stick to jaws
17	50	150	150	0.1411	Wrinkled seal, stick to jaws
18	50	150	160	0.016556	Wrinkled seal, stick to jaws
19	50	150	170	0.006143	With pellets in, otherwise it sticked to the jaws
20	50	150	180	2.8742	With pellets in, otherwise it sticked to the jaws
9	40	160	150	#DIV/0!	Stick to jaws
10	40	160	160	#DIV/0!	Stick to jaws
11	40	160	170	#DIV/0!	Stick to jaws
12	40	160	180	#DIV/0!	Stick to jaws
21	50	160	150	#DIV/0!	Stick to jaws
22	50	160	160	#DIV/0!	Stick to jaws
23	50	160	170	#DIV/0!	Stick to jaws
24	50	160	180	#DIV/0!	Stick to jaws

3.2.2. Summary

This deliverable demonstrates the circular use of PE PCRs coming from tracer-based-sorted (TBS) flexible food packaging waste. First, PE PCRs were produced from TBS food packaging waste, followed by the production of flexible packaging materials. These materials were subsequently used for packaging food products at NESTLÉ. The project demonstrators, which include both food and non-food packaging applications, are presented in Figure 26.

Figure 26: CIRCULAR FoodPack Demonstrators: 3 for food packaging from left to right: coffee in pillow bag, cocoa powder in stand-up-pouch, espresso in gusseted bag format.

The input waste quantities, responsible partners for input waste materials, partners involved in purification, recycling processes and post-treatment, output material quantities, and the type of the demonstrators are summarised below:

LOOP 3 Cycle 1 (L3C1):

- **Waste input:** Approximately **390 kg** of tracer-marked flexible food packaging, including printed tracers, was produced at AMCOR/NESTLÉ. Additionally, **600 kg** of flexible household packaging waste was supplied by SUEZ in France. From this French flexible household packaging waste, 315 kg was incorporated as background waste to the tracer-marked pouches at a 1:1 ratio. The TBS reached a sorting purity of 97.4% and a yield of 90.2%.
- **PE PCR Production:** Following the tracer-based (TB) sorting trials conducted by POLY, the sorted food packaging items underwent shredding, washing, deinking (UGENT), densification and mechanical recycling (SUEZ), and deodorization (KREYEN) processes, as outlined in WP3. These processes resulted in the production of approximately **203 kg** of PE PCR, referred to as L3C1 PE PCRs.
- **Output:** About **249 kg** of PE-based mono-material laminate was produced by AMCOR, combining both virgin PE and PE PCR. This laminate achieved a total L3C1 PE PCR content of **50%** by utilizing a triplex structure, with the PE PCR film (~60 µm) sandwiched between two functional barriers. Barrier characterizations were performed at Fraunhofer and AMCOR, as detailed in Section 2.2.3 of this deliverable. Additional data on the mechanical properties of this PE-based mono-material laminate (L3C1 laminate) with 50% L3C1 PE PCRs for flexible food packaging are available in the confidential deliverable **D5.4** (Month 30).

- **Packaging of food products:** Coffee-filled packs in a pillow bag format (~179 kg) were produced at Nestlé. In addition, sachet packs (~31 kg) were manufactured using the same laminate at AMCOR's customer facility, MESPAC, resulting in a total of approximately **210 kg** of packaged products. These packs, made from the novel flexible packaging laminates (L3C1 laminate) containing L3C1 PE PCRs, were used as input waste for LOOP 3 Cycle 2. Shelf-life predictions, based on the water vapor transmission rate of the produced laminates, were conducted for two food products—coffee and cocoa. Their product lifetimes were validated with the newly developed laminate structure.

LOOP 3 Cycle 2 (L3C2):

- **Waste input:** The coffee-filled packs and sachets produced in Cycle 1 were reused as input waste for Cycle 2, totalling **210 kg**.
- **PE PCR Production:** PE PCR production continued in Cycle 2, utilizing the input waste from Cycle 1. A total of **100 kg** of L3C2 PE PCR was produced. The lower yield of PE PCR in this cycle resulted from multiple trials conducted to optimize the UGENT deinking process. Nearly half of the material was lost during small-scale trials focused on process development and scavenger testing.
- **Output:** Approximately **60 kg** of PE-based mono-material laminate was produced by AMCOR. This laminate incorporated both virgin PE and PE PCR, achieving an optimized L3C2 PE PCR content of 34%. It featured a triplex structure with a PE PCR film (~40 µm) sandwiched between two functional barriers. Mechanical characterizations were performed at Fraunhofer and AMCOR, as detailed in Section 3.1 of this deliverable.
- **Packaging of food products:** Cocoa packs were produced by AMCOR in two formats—stand-up pouch and pillow bag—using the novel laminate containing L3C2 PE PCRs. (shelf-life validation predicted by the shelf-life modelling tool at NESTLE).

It can be concluded that the flexible packaging materials produced using the PE PCRs derived from LOOP 3 input waste - Tracer-Based-Sorted food packaging - meet the requirements for the selected food packaging demonstrators. Table 12 summarizes the properties measured for the laminates produced using PE PCRs in two different types of demonstrators. The first type includes laminates made with PE PCRs from Cycle 1 (L3C1), designed for gusseted/pillow bags used in coffee packaging. The second type features laminates produced with PE PCRs from Cycle 2 (L3C2), intended for pillow bags and stand-up pouches (SUP) used in cocoa packaging. The measured properties are compared against the product specifications outlined in this deliverable.

Table 12: Targeted food packaging demonstrator specifications in comparison to measurements

Criteria	Gusseted bag – Coffee pack	Measurements	SUP - Cacao powder	Measurements
COF (dynamic/static) inside/metal outside/metal	Smooth curve < 0.35 dyn. / 0.4 static	Inside – metal: 0.34 dynamic / 0.40 static outside – metal: 0.40 dynamic / 0.46 static	Smooth curve < 0,35 dyn. / 0,4 static	Inside – metal: 0.24 dynamic / 0.30 static outside – metal: 0.51 dynamic / 0.60 static
Bi-oriented film in structure	At least 20µm	26 µm	At least 20µm	At least 20µm
Bond strength [N/15mm]	2 - 5 N	4.8 (PE PCR↔PE/EvOH/PE) 1.5 (MDOPE/P/SiOx↔PE PCR)	2- 5	5.99 (PE PCR↔PE/EvOH/PE) 2.5 (MDOPE/P/SiOx↔PE PCR)
Seal strength [N/15mm]	>25	20-30 N	> 25	> 40
Stiffness (MD, GPa)	>= 20 µm x 1.5 GPa		>= 20 µm x 1,5 GPa	>= 20 µm x 1,5 GPa
WVTR (38°C, 90%RH)	<1.4 g/m ² /d	Flat: 1.46 & 1.42 g/m²/d Bag: 18.1 & 18.8 mg/(pack-d)	<5 g/d/sq.m	NA
OTR (23°C, 50%RH)	<0.5 cc/d/m ²	Flat: 0.000801 cc/d/sqm Bag: 0.0049 & 0.0064 cc/(pack-d-bar)	<600 cc/d/sq.m	NA
PCR content	30% wt laminate VOC safety limit according to AMCOR < 20 geld/dm ³ with D > 200µm MFI goal of 0,8-4 g/10min	50% PE PCR wt. laminate VOC safety limit ☑ MFI = 0,812 g/10min (190°C, 2,16kg)	30% wt laminate VOC safety limit according to Fraunhofer < 20 geld/dm ³ with D > 200µm MFI goal of 0,8-4 g/10min	34% PE PCR wt. laminate VOC safety limit ☑ MFI = 1,051 g/10min (190°C, 2,16kg)
Overall thickness	Typically 80 µm – below 120µm	126.7 µm	Typically 80 µm	127 µm

(the green color represents the measured values fulfilling the requirements. The orange color shows when they are out of the specification range)

• Life Cycle Assessment:

The life cycle assessment (LCA) of this scenario, which involves tracer-based sorting of recyclable food packaging, recycling through water-based deinking, mechanical recycling, and subsequent deodorization, along with the incorporation of PE PCR into food packaging using a double-barrier concept, has been thoroughly evaluated in Deliverable D7.5: “Guidelines from Final Comprehensive Sustainability Assessment” by UGENT. The assessment compares this approach to other scenarios explored in WP6.

The results indicate that the newly developed technologies—tracer-based sorting and advanced physical recycling—outperform conventional end-of-life methods such as incineration with energy recovery and landfill in managing non-recyclable post-consumer flexible packaging waste. For instance, replacing virgin materials with 34% post-consumer recyclates (PE PCRs) derived from household flexible packaging waste can significantly reduce environmental impact, including a 56% reduction in climate change impact per square meter of flexible food packaging when compared to virgin non-recyclable packaging.

• Market Potential of PE PCRs:

The PE PCRs demonstrate strong market potential, driven by the increasing demand for recycled PE at competitive prices. PE PCRs produced using LOOP 3 technologies, including TBS and advanced physical recycling, present viable business opportunities with costs comparable to virgin PE. Deliverable D8.4: “Feasibility parameters and investment analysis” by NTUA provides detailed cost analyses. The findings estimate the production cost of recycled PE through LOOP 3 technologies at approximately 1.45 €/kg. Furthermore, packaging films containing PE PCR are shown to be economically viable for both food and non-food applications, with a competitive price of around 1.50 €/m², aligning closely with current market rates.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable demonstrates the successful circular use of polyethylene (PE) post-consumer recyclates (PCRs) derived from Tracer-Based-Sorted (TBS) flexible food packaging waste (LOOP 3). PE-based flexible packaging items were marked with fluorescent tracers, sorted, and then subjected to various recycling processes, including shredding, washing, water-based deinking, mechanical recycling, and deodorization.

Two types of food packaging demonstrators were produced. The first cycle (LOOP 3 Cycle 1) involved coffee packaging containing 50% PE PCR content. The second cycle (LOOP 3 Cycle 2) involved cocoa powder packaging, utilizing PE PCRs produced from Cycle 1 as input waste.

The PE PCRs produced in both cycles were successfully used to create new flexible packaging materials. Despite some challenges, including the presence of gels and slightly reduced mechanical properties in Cycle 2, the recyclates could be used effectively in food packaging materials with a PCR content of 34%.

The tracer-based sorting system demonstrated high purity, exceeding 98%, with even higher purity using Sort4Circle® technology. The recycling processes did not significantly impact the performance of the materials, though further improvements are needed to reduce the presence of gels in the films.

The incorporation of functional barriers was crucial for ensuring the safety of the packaging by reducing the migration of unwanted substances into the packaged food. The use of two functional barriers in the laminate structure improved the safety but resulted in a more complex material compared to virgin packaging materials.

While the project achieved promising results, further research is needed to optimize material properties, confirm the long-term effectiveness of functional barriers in reducing contamination, and simplify testing procedures. Additionally, further investigation into certified recycling methods for PE PCR production is recommended.

The deliverable also mentions the sustainability and feasibility of using PE PCRs for food packaging, with detailed assessments of environmental impacts and costs provided in other public deliverables (D7.5 and D8.4). The results show that the use of PE PCRs reduces the environmental impact compared to virgin materials.

